

Appendix B: Grism spectra

In Figs. B.1, B.2, B.2, B.2 and B.3 we show NIRISS grism spectra used to obtain spectroscopic redshifts of multiple images in this work. All fits, apart from K87.2, used only the grism spectrum. For K87.2, only the combined fit of the grism spectrum and photometry returned the correct redshift in agreement with K87.1 and K87.3. We note that its spectrum contains clear [OIII] and [OII] emission in agreement with other images of the system. Images K95.1, K95.3, K90.1, K90.3 and C2.3 were re-fitted with a narrower redshift prior (± 1 or ± 0.5) where the redshift range was estimated based on other images of the system with more reliable fits (grism or NIRSpec prism) and corroborated by other arguments (several visually discernible emission lines, photometric redshifts etc.). We note that the grism redshifts of those images agree with other multiple images of the system within the spectroscopic redshift uncertainty, which is much narrower than the chosen prior range. We also note that the spectrum of K82.1 in GR150C grism orientation is aligned with the direction of the arc, resulting in a collapsed 1D spectrum without visible emission lines. However, the spectrum in GR150R orientation shows several emission lines, and the combined fit of a narrow spectral range returns a reliable redshift of 2.03 ± 0.02 .

Fig. B.1: NIRISS F115W, F150W and F200W grism spectra of the newly discovered (CANUCS) multiple images. The RGB cutouts are composed of JWST/NIRCam and HST/WFC3 images (F277W, F356W, F410M, F444W in red, F115W, F150W, F200W in green and F814W, F606W, F435W and F090W in blue) with indicated angular scale and the GR150R and GR150C grism dispersion directions. The upper row represents 1D spectra in different filters, showing only the spectral range used for redshift fitting (see Sect. 2.2). In the plots, we indicate contamination and wavelengths of visible emission lines. The grey-shaded region represents the spectral range where the filter transmission falls below one-half of the maximal value. The second and the third rows include 2D spectra in each filter, and for each orientation that was used to obtain redshift - highly contaminated spectra are not displayed.

Fig. B.2: NIRISS spectra of known multiple image candidates with previously unknown system redshift. The figure is analogous to Fig. B.1.

Fig. B.2: continued

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Fig. B.3: NIRISS spectra, not included in previous figures but also used in this work, either for updating the system redshift (K5 and K8a.1), confirming a new multiple image candidate (K26.3) or showing the spectral line found in the spectra of counter images (K33.4). The figure is analogous to Figs. B.1 and B.2.

Fig. B.4: JWST/NIRCam and HST/WCS (F277W, F356W, F410M, F444W in red, F115W, F150W, F200W in green and F814W, F606W, F435W, F090W in blue) cutouts spanning $1.2''$ showing multiple images of new CANUCS systems, not included in the Di24 catalog. Multiple images, marked with asterisk (*) are spectroscopically confirmed and are also shown in Fig. B.1 with their grism spectra. The colour of the labels indicates the category (gold, silver, or bronze, depending on their reliability).

Fig. B.4: continued